

Technical Supplement to the Medical Education Corpus

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This technical supplement is intended to outline — in brief but complete detail — all the steps taken to develop and evaluate the MEC Classifier. The MEC Classifier is a machine learning model that was used to create the Medical Education Corpus (MEC), the first dedicated collection of medical education papers. The intended audience has an understanding of machine learning, however clarification statements were added to make this as widely understandable as possible. This technical supplement is intended to be read with the original MEC paper.

We treated this problem as a machine learning classification problem. There is class imbalance — our randomly sampled validation set (Labeling Phase 2a) had 24 of 500 papers as medical education = 4.8%. Class imbalance in general makes classification more challenging, as without careful consideration a model could learn to always predict the majority class (in this case predicting “not medical education” every time).

This class imbalance also made random sampling for training data infeasible for our team. We would need to label 5000 papers to obtain ~240 medical education papers, and that would still likely be an insufficient number of medical education papers for training. This number of labels was prohibitive because our labeling process was expensive (two independent labels assigned by the author team; not outsourced to ensure quality).

We first trialed a balanced training set (Labeling Phase 1) using existing PubMed labels and fortunately already demonstrated acceptable performance. We then went on to complete the coverage of all journals (Labeling Phase 3a), and then began utilizing active learning to specifically sample training papers in the areas that the model was making errors (Labeling Phase 4a, 4b).

Our training process was relatively simple. We relied heavily on an existing model, SPECTER2 from the Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence.¹ SPECTER2 embeddings are generated from paper titles with optional abstracts, and are specifically tuned for scientific document classification / search / suggestions. We treated this as a supervised learning problem and the SVM (support vector machine) architecture was highly performant for our purposes (and was the same architecture tested in the SPECTER2 development).

The use of SPECTER2 embeddings motivated using Semantic Scholar, also managed by the Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence.² On Semantic Scholar, most papers have SPECTER2 embeddings precomputed. Also, in our testing (not shown), papers that did not have abstracts available via the API (likely due to publisher agreements) still often had SPECTER2 embeddings available that reflected the input of the abstract. Semantic Scholar is also openly-accessible.

Data Sampling and Labeling

All labeled data is separately uploaded with Semantic Scholar ID, assigned label (medical education or not), data split (training, validation, testing), labeling phase, journal name, abstract, URL, PMID, MeSH terms (from Entrez API), and the paper's SPECTER2 embedding (either from Semantic Scholar API or computed from available title and abstract if needed using the SPECTER2 model from HuggingFace).

Labeling Phase	Goal	Sampling Method	Number of Papers	Used for
1 March 2024	Initial training sample To obtain a first set of papers to train the model.	For 123 journals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 21 journals from MEJ-Core (<i>Focus on Health Professions Education</i> was not yet indexed on Semantic Scholar, <i>Canadian Medical Education Journal</i> and <i>JGME</i> were inadvertently initially excluded) - The 102 additional journals from the Citation Impact journal list <p>We sampled 6 medical education and 6 non-medical education papers, selected with PubMed as below. (Not all journals had 6 of each available)</p>	1371	Training
2a August 2024	Validation sample To obtain a sample of papers which matches the underlying distribution	500 papers were selected from the MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent using stratified random sampling by journal size	500	Validation
2b August 2024	Excess validation labels A handful of additional papers were labeled during the sampling process	In the course of performing the stratified sampling, an additional 45 papers were labeled before being probabilistically excluded from the validation set. This is because some journals were due fractional papers (e.g. 0.4 papers) based on journal size. Such papers were randomly included (e.g. 40% chance for 0.4 papers), and the sampling was repeated until 500 papers exactly were obtained for ease of calculations. The excluded 45 papers compose 2b.	45	Training

<p>3a</p> <p>October 2024</p>	<p>Annotated Bibliography coverage</p> <p>To complete the coverage of Annotated Bibliography journals</p>	<p>We trained our classifier on Labeling Phase 1 and 2b.</p> <p>Then for the journals in the Annotated Bibliography that were not already included in the above (25 journals), we sampled 6 that our classifier thought was medical education, and 6 that the classifier thought was not medical education (active learning).</p> <p>We utilized k-means clustering to select 6 medoids from each category to increase the representativeness of our samples.³ (<i>Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education</i> did not have any the model thought was medical education)</p>	<p>294</p>	<p>Training</p>
<p>3b</p> <p>October 2024</p>	<p>Active learning</p> <p>To reduce the false positive rate of the classifier by labeling “hard positives” (papers the model classifies as medical education, but that have high uncertainty)</p>	<p>The classifier outputs a decision score. The sign (positive/negative) of the decision score represents whether the model thinks the paper is medical education or not. The magnitude of the decision score approximates the model’s “confidence” in its classification. Decision scores from -1 to +1 is the area with the most model uncertainty.</p> <p>We sampled the “hard positives,” meaning the decision score from 0 to 1 for all papers in the MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent.</p> <p>We utilized k-means clustering to select the 200 medoids to increase the representativeness of our samples.³ (198 clusters were created, and 2 papers were duplicate from 3a)</p>	<p>196</p>	<p>Training</p>
<p>4a</p> <p>October 2024</p>	<p>MEJ-Core venues coverage</p> <p>To complete the coverage of the inadvertently excluded venues and the newly indexed venue.</p>	<p>We trained our classifier on all prior data excluding validation data (Labeling Phase 1, 2b, 3a, 3b)</p> <p>Then for <i>Canadian Medical Education Journal</i>, <i>Journal of Graduate Medical Education</i>, and <i>Focus on Health Professional Education</i> (see Labeling Phase 1), we sampled 6 that our classifier thought was medical education, and 6 that the classifier thought was not medical education.</p> <p>We utilized k-means clustering to select 6 medoids from each category to increase the representativeness of our samples. We sampled 6 “hard negatives,” meaning decision scores from -1 to 0, and 6 “hard positives,” meaning decision scores from 0 to 1.</p>	<p>36</p>	<p>Training</p>

<p>4b</p> <p>October 2024</p>	<p>Discrepant venues</p> <p>To sample allied health venues and BMJ for more precise</p>	<p>We trained our classifier on all prior data excluding validation data (Labeling Phase 1, 2b, 3a, 3b)</p> <p>We applied this classifier to all papers in the MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent, and obtained the fraction of each journal’s papers that was classified as medical education.</p> <p>We hand-selected these venues based on the hypothesis that “veterinary medical education” or “physician assistant education” was overlapping with “medical education” in the classifier:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Journal of Veterinary Medical Education</i> - <i>The Journal of Physician Assistant Education</i> - <i>BMJ</i> as it is contributing over 6000 medical education papers and we wanted to reduce the false positive rate. <p>From each venue we chose 30 papers from the positive decision score range.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For <i>Journal of Veterinary Medical Education</i> and <i>The Journal of Physician Assistant Education</i> the top 30 highest decision scores were chosen, as upon inspection very few were medical education papers. - For <i>BMJ</i>, k-means clustering was used to select 30 medoids from the 0 to 0.5 range (chosen by inspection of the results) 	<p>3 x 30 = 90</p>	<p>Training</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent Test Set</p>	<p>From the MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent, a stratified random sample of 1500 papers were chosen, excluding the already sampled papers. The total number of papers was 2.3 million, so including or excluding the already sampled papers did not meaningfully change the number of papers due to each journal based on stratification.</p>	<p>1500</p>	<p>Testing</p>

PubMed Search for Phase 1a

With each identified journal, LM and JC — both experienced librarians — created a Medical Education search hedge. The search hedges were combined with each journal’s ISSN then entered into a Python script (not shown). The Python script was used to create a loop that would query E-Utilities — the public API to the National Center for Biotechnology Information’s (NCBI) Entrez system.⁴ For each journal, we searched for ISSN AND Medical Education then ISSN NOT Medical Education. The idea was to capture articles from each journal that met PubMed’s indexing

for Medical Education or didn't. Then, we created a sub-process step that would randomize each journal's results and retrieve the first six articles for that journal. This allowed us to be blinded to the randomization process.

Total Number of Papers

- 2032 in the training split
- 500 in the validation split
- 1500 in the testing split

Training and Evaluation

Input features:

- SPECTER2 embedding of the title and abstract of the paper to classify. Where available, we obtained these from the Semantic Scholar API. Otherwise we computed them from the title and abstract using the SPECTER2 model on HuggingFace.
- The average SPECTER2 embedding of the journal that the paper is published in. We computed this by downloading all papers in a particular journal and averaging their SPECTER2 embeddings.

Chosen model parameters (selected based on Labeling Phase 1, 2b, 3a, 3b, 4a, 4b evaluated against Validation set):

C = 1

gamma = 5

kernel = rbf

Environment details: scikit-learn 1.4.2 on Python 3.12.6.

Test Results

The model was trained on the 2032 training + 500 validation papers = 2532 papers. It was tested on the 1500 test papers. To reproduce the test results, download and follow in the instructions in the `mec_code.py` file.

The resulting output is below. On a 2022 MacBook Air with 8GB RAM, the script completes in less than 5 minutes on first run (predominantly waiting on first sklearn import). Subsequent runs complete in about 2 minutes.

```
===== Loading and processing Data =====
```

```
Data shapes:
```

```
X_train (including validation): (2532, 1536)
```

```
X_test (mej_core_adjacent): (1500, 1536)
```

```
y_train (including validation): (2532,)
```

```
y_test (mej_core_adjacent): (1500,)
```

```
Class distributions:
```

```
Training set (including validation):
```

```
0    0.674961
```

```
1    0.325039
```

Name: proportion, dtype: float64

Test set (mej_core_adjacent):

0 0.947333

1 0.052667

Name: proportion, dtype: float64

==== Train and evaluate model on Semantic Scholar data =====

Model Performance on Training Set:

F1: 0.941

Precision: 0.945

Recall: 0.938

Model Performance on Test Set:

F1: 0.834

Precision: 0.810

Recall: 0.861

==== Evaluate on PubMed subset =====

There are 1358 PubMed papers in the test data.

Performance on PubMed Subset:

MEC Classifier:

F1: 0.859

Precision: 0.821

Recall: 0.901

'Education, Medical' MeSH:

F1: 0.656

Precision: 0.784

Recall: 0.563

All Medical-Education-Related MeSH Terms:

F1: 0.729

Precision: 0.810

Recall: 0.662

McNemar's Test Results (MEC vs All Medical-Education MeSH):

Sensitivity comparison:

Contingency table: [[43, 4], [21, 3]]

Chi-squared: 10.240

p-value: 0.00137

Specificity comparison:

Contingency table: [[1265, 11], [8, 3]]

Chi-squared: 8.000

p-value: 0.64761

==== Train final model on all data ====

Final model training complete.

==== Interactive paper prediction ====

Enter a Semantic Scholar ID: 48acb67dc940142d1b35cdf4aaad75c70f45c3c6

Journal: Family Medicine

Title: Motivational interviewing workshop in a virtual world: learning as avatars.

Abstract: BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Limited research has been done to understand outcomes of continuing medical education offered in three-dimensional, immersive virtual worlds. We studied a case of a virtual w...

Decision score: 0.885

Classification: Medical Education

Statistical Tests

We utilized McNemar's chi-squared test to compare sensitivity and specificity as this was a binary classification task using a single test set.⁵

Generating the MEC

Using the MEC Classifier to generate the MEC requires downloading all 2.3 million papers in the MEJ-Core and MEJ-Adjacent from the Semantic Scholar API.⁶ This process involves handling approximately 15GB of data and requires moderate computational resources (to compute the missing SPECTER2 embeddings) and database storage (to hold the embedding data). Due to these implementation-specific requirements, users will need to develop their own data pipeline based on their computational resources. We recommend starting with a small subset of journals to test the pipeline before scaling to the full corpus.

References

1. Singh A, D'Arcy M, Cohan A, Downey D, Feldman S. SciRepEval: a multi-format benchmark for scientific document representations. In: *Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing.* ; 2022. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:254018137>
2. Fricke S. Semantic Scholar. *J Med Libr Assoc JMLA.* 2018;106(1):145-147. doi:10.5195/jmla.2018.280
3. Kremer J, Steenstrup Pedersen K, Igel C. Active learning with support vector machines. *WIRES Data Min Knowl Discov.* 2014;4(4):313-326. doi:10.1002/widm.1132
4. Sayers EW, Bolton EE, Brister JR, et al. Database resources of the national center for biotechnology information. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2022;50(D1):D20-D26. doi:10.1093/nar/gkab1112
5. Rainio O, Teuho J, Klén R. Evaluation metrics and statistical tests for machine learning. *Sci Rep.* 2024;14(1):6086. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-56706-x
6. Kinney R, Anastasiades C, Authur R, et al. The Semantic Scholar Open Data Platform. Published online 2023. doi:10.48550/ARXIV.2301.10140